

360° Educational Robotics Project Management for High Abilities and Gifted Students

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Abstract

This paper presents the results of a project that analysed Specialized Educational Assistance (AEE) for High Abilities and Gifted Students (AH/SD) aged 7 to 15 in two public schools in the Federal District over a period of 24 months. The work was developed through a partnership between University of Brasília (UnB) and the State Department of Education of the Federal District (SEEDF). This project enabled the implementation of two educational robotics laboratories, acquisition of electronic devices (five educational robotic kits and two kits for assembling 3D printers), among other materials. The project also provided scholarships for Mechatronics and Computer Engineering students at the university as well as opportunities for teacher training, including support for the monitors and students in class throughout the project period. It was also possible to develop a system to control the attendance to AH/SD students. The objective of this study consisted of inserting Educational Robotics (RE) in attendance to AH/SD students and evaluating scientific knowledge in the field of robotics and cognitive development through workshops aimed at stimulating skills, creative thinking, cooperation, interpersonal relationships, and problem solving. It also aimed at sharing a successful experience that combined the contents conveyed to students of graduate, undergraduate and technical level courses in the execution of the lesson planning. Thus, this paper presents an ER project management model with a multidisciplinary team that contributed to the technological learning process in basic education and obtained a successful result.

Keywords: Educational Robotics; High Abilities and Gifted Students; ER laboratory.

1 Introduction

Educational Robotics (ER), also called Pedagogical Robotics, provides opportunities for students to learn and practice abilities and skills in several areas of knowledge, such as physics, algebra, geometry, design, electronics, mechanics and computer programming. In addition to providing interdisciplinary learning, ER consists of a significant tool for student development when it comes to the desirable aspects of the theoretical and methodological model adopted in the Specialized Educational Service to High-Ability and Gifted Students (AEE-AH/SD) in the Federal District (DF), Brazil. The work described in this paper had the main goal of evaluating the impact of ER in the cognitive development of students with high abilities as well as to implement ER laboratories for High Abilities and Gifted Students (AH/SD) attended by the specialized service.

1.1 Robotics and Educational Robotics Concept

Robotics is a multidisciplinary area in engineering that not only comprises abundant research studies in the development and application of robots but also provides opportunities for the study of computational thinking and experimentation methods in the classroom.

Therefore, the term "robotics" does not only refer to a set of automated machines that accelerate the production system but it has also been as an instrument for multidisciplinary teaching in schools (Chang, 2010). It is believed that the use of ER in classrooms has a positive impact on student learning and that it can be seen as a new learning strategy (Liyang & Baichang, 2018).

ER is a very promising area of knowledge that shows the potential of learning methods such as observation, knowledge of basic concepts electronics, programming, appropriate teaching pedagogy obtained through teacher training, and monitoring of classes through periodic evaluations (Ya-Wen, 2018).

ER has been shown to promote students' creative attitude, communication skills, systemic vision, cooperation and teamwork, as well as to favor increased interest and motivation to learn traditional disciplines in the regular teaching curriculum (Chang, 2010).

1.2 Resources needed in ER

The learning environment of ER usually includes resources such as computers, softwares, as well as electronic and electromechanical components. Through the integration of these elements, students build and program automated devices with the objective of exploring concepts from different areas of knowledge (Peleg & Baram-Tsabari, 2017).

The development of robotic devices for educational purposes is a multidisciplinary activity that not only involves theoretical studies related to STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) but can also indirectly address other areas such as biology, chemistry, and languages (Benitti, 2012).

The inclusion of ER contents favors students as for improving visualization of abstract concepts such as vectors, forces, gravity, geometry, electromagnetism, among others (Karim, Lemaignan & Mondada, 2015). Therefore, ER can benefit the learning process of mathematics and physics in elementary, middle, and high school.

Regarding the development of activities of non-specifically technical learning, studies (Kopcha, 2017) indicate that conventional education still needs to evolve. Most studies report that robots play a positive role in the development of creative thinking as well as improve social skills and logical reasoning for problem solving. In addition, interaction with robots increases motivation, engagement and creates a positive attitude towards ER education among children (Blikstein, 2013).

ER is not included in the regular basic education curriculum of public schools in Brazil. However, private schools have shown growing interest in this area, often investing in after-school programs or independent projects such as robotics laboratories, and organization and participation in events such as olympiads and exhibitions.

Blikstein (2013) advocates for linking intellectual work in the classroom with students' ability to build things, either with their parents or friends in garages, or in companies and schools (Blikstein, 2013).

The approach of robotics in schools, which can involve technological methodology, presents a significant potential for pedagogical changes, especially due to students' interest in building robots and developing projects using electronic and mechanical components.

In order to increase student's awareness about sustainable development, this paper proposes building robots with reusable material and the use of free programming platforms of educational robots. By doing so, it is possible to experience the advent of a new era for educational technology learning (Eguchi, 2010; Gershenfeld, 2007).

1.3 Development of cognitive skills

Over the last years, ER attracted the interest of education professionals as a powerful resource for developing skills, especially cognitive ones, in students of Basic Education, strengthening science learning, mathematics, technology, informatics, and other interdisciplinary subjects.

In the literature, ER covers knowledge and transversal skills in STEM areas, such as subject-oriented knowledge (e.g., knowledge of physics, mathematics etc.) and cognitive skills (e.g., analysis, classification, and prediction). Consideration of the practice domain, troubleshooting process, engineering design process and scientific research skills characterize ER (Toulmin, 2007).

Other important abilities to personal development include cognitive, meta-cognitive and social skills, such as research skills, creative thinking, decision making, problem solving, communication skills and team work. All of which are necessary in ER laboratories.

Eck et al. (2013) reported that infants improved their resistance and ability to concentrate for a certain period as well as developed planning and cognitive flexibility apply to learning abstract rules. Most studies about ER emphasize cognitive domains and skills more than the attitude domain (Keren & Fridin, 2014).

According Mataric (2000), robots assist in children's cognitive and intellectual development (Mataric, 2000). Hmelo-Silver & Pfeffer, (2004) explain the importance of cognitive processes for restrict complex problems, logics, algorithms, application of rules, decision-making, strategic performance, and more detailed descriptive analyses of complexity and problem typology (Hmelo-Silver & Pfeffer, 2004).

Kandhofer (2012) argues that research needs to prove if the learning objectives have been achieved in each project, that is, if more children are interested in science and technology and have developed cognitive/social skills significantly better. In addition, proponents need to observe whether the robotic design for young children has an impact on their educational career, which requires longitudinal evaluation of projects (Kandhofer et al., 2012).

2 Methodology

This work consisted of applying ER activities to students with high skills/Giftedness. The activities were presented by groups in two schools. Students were aged between 7 and 15.

The two schools have an average of 40 students each, thus divided from regular education: elementary school (2nd, 3rd, 4th, and 5th grades), middle school (6th, 7th, and 8th grades), and high school (9th and 10th grades). The attendance hours took place once a week in the morning (from 8a.m. to 12a.m.) and in the afternoon (from 2pm. to 6p.m.). Students were aggregated by affinity, not necessarily by age groups but by interests in specific subjects. This work was performed in five steps:

- Teacher training.
- Acquisition of materials and construction of the ER laboratories.
- Selection of monitors at University of Brasília.
- Planning classes with teachers that attend to highly-Skilled/gifted students.
- System development on high skills and giftedness.

The work team was formed by five undergraduate students in Mechatronics Engineering, one undergraduate student in Computer Engineering, two high school students (one in Computer Technician course and one in Electronic Technician course), two professors at the university, two teachers at the State Department of Education of the Federal District (SEEDF), one doctoral student and one master's student in Mechanical Engineering, along with the project coordinator.

2.1 Teacher training

Teacher preparation to start ER classes require the proposition of a robotics teaching model that mixes the tangibility of the robots with the possibility of development of various contents. Teachers are essential resources in the educational structure. They need to feel confident about using the tools and methods used to build robots (Kradolfer, Dubois, Riedo, Mondada, & Fassa, 2014).

Such confidence can only be achieved through appropriate training and active/proactive involvement. Many of the teachers feel hesitant in dealing with robotics in the classroom. Such behavior reflects their reluctance in learning new concepts, which can sometimes be associated with the absence of robotics in the standard curriculum as well as with the fact that the learning outcome is achieved in the long term (Shuttleworth, 2018).

The content of the ER course was designed and ministered over a period of 6 months, and the project trained 30 teachers from the Federal District. This training was prioritized for teachers that provide assistance to AH/SD students. The training contents consisted of basic notions of electronics, free software programming, scratch, and usage of microcontrollers (Arduino), and various electronic devices.

The programme diversity, in terms of interaction approaches and addressed themes, transforms PAEE/ALE in a platform for those who wish to share and learn more about active learning and project oriented approaches to teaching/learning of engineering.

2.2 Materials Acquired and Construction of Laboratories

In the course of the teacher training, during the initial 6 months of the project, each school involved in the study provided a classroom for mounting the laboratories (Figure 1). Both had approximately 25m². They were equipped with chairs and tables covered with rubber blankets, and cabinets for accommodating support materials. In addition, several electronic devices were purchased: microcontrollers, mounting kits for 3D printers, five educational robotics kits, and 10 laptops.

Figure 1. Educational Robotics Laboratory.

2.3 Selection of Scholarship Students

Professors/researchers of University of Brasília performed the selection of monitors for supporting school teachers that attend to AH/SD students. The selected tutors were five undergraduate students in Mechatronics Engineering and one in Computer Engineering, all of whom mastered ER content. All fellows were guided by the team of teachers.

2.4 Lesson Planning

The planning involved the collective documentation of the content taught in the resource room (laboratory), by separating materials for building prototypes, installing programs, setting machines, searching content with references, and accessing research through the Internet. For instance, if creating a robot is an activity to be performed, then a problem is generated, and one should use creativity to come up with a robot proposal. Several questions must be answered: How should the robot move? By using wheels or legs, or by crawling? What will be the energy source to be used? What materials ought to be used? What will be its shape? Will it look like a cart, a human or a spider? How will it be controlled? The answer to these and other questions should be based on discussions and search for solutions in magazines, books, films or on the Internet. After conception, one should move on to the construction phase, which will contribute to the development or improvement of manual skills, for it will be necessary to design, cut, fit, glue, screw, paint, and weld components, among other actions.

2.5 System development for High Abilities and Gifted Students

A system was created to register the students to be attended, teachers, and schools of the Federal District with resource rooms for AH/SD students as well as to generate specific reports about the activities to be developed. This system was intended to decrease the number of reports and the filling out of paper forms, speeding the issuance of records and response to service inquiries. The system is currently in the testing phase, holding a database fed with more than 700 registered students.

3 Results

The results obtained from the project developed were significant. It was possible to assemble two ER laboratories, provide professional training for teachers, participate in annual events inherent to ER, and acquire

materials for student use (educational robotics kits, electronic devices, and one 3D printer) as well as support for handling them.

Therefore, it was possible to develop individual projects with students of the prototype building service using the materials acquired in the laboratory.

Social skills were acquired through participation and research to solve problems related to the ER proposed activities.

The monitors, students, and guiding researchers obtained experience in the content approached. The former group received participation grants, and support in class was provided to them as well as to teachers and students.

4 Discussion and Conclusion

Despite the scientific progress in this project, one identified the potential limitations of the education system as a whole when it comes to implementing emerging Educational Robotics in its schools (Renzulli, 2012), mainly in terms of infrastructure and acquisition of materials for the opening of the laboratories (ranging from electronic devices to 3D printers).

The greatest challenge of this work was not only convincing the teachers regarding the relevance of Robotics but also training them and developing the content modules of ER based on the regular curriculum of basic education.

The challenges were minimized by the teacher training course, development of class tutorials, and monitor support, which in fact brought confidence to the development of classes along with the school teachers responsible for their respective ER research laboratories.

ER should be interpreted as a discipline to promote essential life skills (cognitive and personal development, and team work). Therefore, it is possible for students to develop their potential imagination, expressing themselves, making original choices, and generating value to their lives. The benefits of ER can be perceived in all children engaged in robotics projects. Therefore, topics related to awakening interest in science and technology should be included in the basic regular curriculum of every school in the Federal District.

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